

USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract: The article analyzes the features of the education system in the context of the formation of the digital economy, reveals the essence of the concepts of the digital economy, information and communication technologies. The main areas are government regulation and digitalization of education.

Keywords: digitalization, digital economy, artificial intelligence, Network Activity Index, open online courses.

Introduction. Currently, the world has entered the era of the fourth industrial revolution, Industry 4.0, which imposes additional conditions on the definition of most types of activities. First of all, the modification covers industry and the economic sector as a whole, but the transformation of this area is impossible without the training of qualified personnel. Focusing on global digitalization, there is a need for more thorough training of specialists both in the subject area and in the field of self-organization and self-learning. It is no secret that in the realities of the 21st century, key issues are relevant, reliable information, including the ability to search for it, analyze and correctly transcribe it, as well as knowledge.

The complication of social structures and relations, increasingly relying on modern digital technologies, brings to the forefront the need to form a new type of economy, the main basis of which is digital technologies. It is this type of economy that is usually designated in modern literature by such concepts as "digital economy" and "digitalization".

Literature review. Many foreign scientists have studied these concepts, including D. Bell, F. Weber and D. Bode, Machlup, A. Riis, A. Toffler, X. Hanamari and D. Wada, K. Arrow. For the first time in the world, the topic of "digitalization" was introduced by the Canadian scientist Don Tapscott in his book "The Digital Society: Pros and Cons of the Age of Networked Intelligence" in 1995 [4, p.102]

Today, the term "digitalization" makes sense to consider in a narrow and broad sense. Digitalization in a narrow sense means the transformation of information into digital form, which implies a reduction in costs and the emergence of new opportunities. Digitalization in the traditional sense means a modern general trend in the development of the economy and society, which is based on the transformation of information into digital form, which should lead to increased economic efficiency and quality of life.

Several authors have argued that education, as an agent of the socialization of knowledge, should take advantage of the benefits of AI in the training context in order to maximize educational achievements. To achieve this purpose, multiple technologies could be applied in the classroom, including virtual reality, augmented reality, AI chats, and video games, among others. These enriching applications promoted the creation of more dynamic and disruptive classrooms, such as the design of virtual environments for instant student exploration. After observing the points of view of various authors on the relationship between AI and education, it was clear that this technology could revolutionize current methods in this sector. The benefits, the challenges, and the applications of AI in education can be

observed clearly in [Figure 1](#). [4]

Figure 1. Benefits, vision, challenges, and applications of artificial intelligence.

At the beginning of 2020, the whole world again turned to the issue of digitalization of education. This interest is associated with the slowdown in scientific and technological progress in the digital sphere, as well as with the emergence of the coronavirus infection "COVID-19", which was quickly recognized as a pandemic. Currently, the education of the future is undergoing a digital transformation, going beyond the time frame of life, due to the change in educational institutions using the unique capabilities of network and digital technologies, with the transformation of all direct and limited participants in the educational process. The role of the teacher is changing in the era of the digital economy, new forms of interaction between teacher and student are being created, the so-called network interaction. [5, p.135] Today, in the context of Uzbekistan, the study of the scientific foundations of the patterns, trends and opportunities for the development of the digital economy, in particular, the deepening of modern information technologies in various areas of the economy, is of particular relevance.

The success of large-scale reforms carried out in the country directly depends on the emergence of new innovations in the national economy. Therefore, improving the digital economy and scientific research in the field of social,

economic, psychological and legal foundations plays my role. According to the network activity index (Networked Readiness Index - a comprehensive indicator characterizing According to the World Economic Forum's Digital Economy Index (the level of development of information and communication technologies in countries around the world) proposed to assess countries' readiness for the digital economy, Uzbekistan ranks 83rd among 121 countries in this ranking. However, according to experts, Uzbeks have the potential to increase the speed of digitalization.

In his Address to the Oliy Majlis, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev identified the widespread introduction of digital technologies in all spheres of the country's socio-economic life as a priority task. [1, p.3] Thus, the State Program adopted within the framework of the Year of Science, Education and Digital Economy Development provided for the development of the Digital Uzbekistan - 2030 strategy.

Today, the digital economy provides up to 15.5% of the world's gross domestic product. Over the past 15 years, the digital economy has grown 2.5 times faster than the world's GDP. Our country plans to double the gross domestic product. The initial step towards the formation, implementation and development of digitalization as a new innovative component of the economy was the adoption of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev dated July 3, 2018 No. PP-3832 "On measures to develop the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan". In essence, this document is a comprehensive strategy for the development of information technology in the country for the next decade. [2, p.36]

The next decade should become an era of change in higher education, the reform of digitalization of education involves equipping educational institutions with modern technology, namely computers with the ability to connect to the Internet, information systems that allow access to educational resources, the results

of modern scientific research and development, electronic scientific libraries in various languages of the world.

Results and discussion. Digitalization makes it possible to quickly and efficiently develop educational and scientific content related to innovative technologies.

This is, first of all, the creation of digital electronic textbooks, manuals and other educational literature, as well as the transfer of the entire monitoring educational system to a digital format. Secondly, digitalization of online learning will provide significant and expected results for both subjects and objects of the learning process. There is full confidence that personnel trained on the basis of digital technologies will become professional pilots of our economy in the competitive environment of the global market.

Digitalization of education leads to serious changes in the labor market and is aimed at reorganizing the educational process, rethinking the role of the teacher. On the one hand, digitalization undermines the methodological base of the school inherited from the past, which has proven its effectiveness, and on the other hand, it creates the availability of information in its various forms. However, the availability of information will require teachers and students to constantly search for and select relevant and interesting content, as well as high speed of processing of the received information.

AI is a broad term that is often used instead of describing the more complex types—or subsets—of AI. However, broadly labeling initiatives as an “AI project” can make selecting the right supporting technology even more difficult. Each AI subset requires a unique combination of hardware, software, and security based on the project’s end goal. Let’s explore the types of AI that are either being used at your institution already or will be soon.

Figure 2. The types of AI

Classical machine learning (ML): Uses models, or algorithms, to analyze data sets, identify patterns, and make predictions without human intervention. This type of AI is often the first type students learn about when beginning their college career. ML also powers many popular tools used by everyone on campus, such as Gradescope, Grammarly, Consensus, Elicit, and ResearchRabbit.

Deep learning: Teaches computers to process data in a way that is inspired by the human brain, using models that can recognize complex patterns in pictures, text, sounds, and other data to produce accurate insights and predictions. This type of AI is an advancement of classical ML and used when working with massive data sets that have numerous parameters or when a high level of accuracy is required.

Computer vision: Trains computers to make sense of the overwhelming amount of visual data collected to locate, identify, and track objects or specific actions. This type of AI combines cameras, edge computing, cloud-based computing, software, and AI to enable systems to “see” data collected from cameras and videos. In addition to researchers using computer vision to aid their pioneering work, it’s often used by campus security and administration professionals to help ensure campus safety. Computer vision can also enhance student engagement in distance learning, enable automated proctoring for online exams, and help spot plagiarism in handwritten student exams.

Generative AI: Generates new content when provided with a prompt by an end user. Generative AI creates this content based on the massive sets of data and machine learning AI algorithms it was trained on. This type of AI is integrated with

language AI, also known as natural language processing (NLP), which allows it to process and understand human language. When used together, generative AI and NLP can understand a prompt and generate an appropriate response via text, video, imagery, or audio. Generative AI is a relatively new tool that higher ed students and professionals are enthusiastically adopting and experimenting with to accelerate research, boost productivity, enhance curriculum development, and maximize learning outcomes.

Conclusion. To summarize and assess the prospects for the development of education in the context of the transition to a digital environment, it can be noted that the process, although in its initial stages, is already characterized by significant changes in approaches to methods and formats. education. Further steps will further integrate education into everyday life in all areas and at all levels of initial training.

But then, educators from different grades realize the benefits of technology in the classroom and beyond. Education is still one of the last industries to undergo and adapt to large-scale changes, and it still works with outdated methods and practices. But there are many educational institutions around the world that understand the benefits of digital transformation and the development of educational technologies. Instructors and teachers have started making major changes to their usual teaching and assessment methods, and it is happening faster too.

Current digital trends in education are making headlines as they are having a huge impact on student learning, from virtual personal assistants for students to built-in CRMs. Digital transformation is helping educational institutions serve better. Today, technology is changing the landscape of higher education dramatically. Educators today are introducing technology into the classroom, from massive open online courses (MOOCs) to flipped classrooms, new methods and ways to improve the learning process for students.

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